

PREDICTORS OF TURNOVER INTENTIONS AMONG NURSE EDUCATORS IN THE PRIVATE INSTITUTIONS OF PAMPANGA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between environmental factors, organizational commitment, and turnover intentions among nurse educators in private institutions in Pampanga, guided by Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory. Employing a quantitative research design, data were collected through survey questionnaires and analyzed using Pearson's correlation and regression techniques. Findings revealed that environmental factors, encompassing both hygiene and motivational elements, were moderately and negatively correlated with turnover intentions, indicating that improved workplace conditions reduce the likelihood of attrition. In contrast, organizational commitment demonstrated a very weak and statistically insignificant relationship with turnover intentions, suggesting limited influence in this context. Regression analysis confirmed that environmental factors alone explained 26.1% of the variance in turnover intentions, while the combined model of environmental factors and organizational commitment accounted for 34.1%, with environmental factors exerting the stronger negative effect. These results underscore the critical role of workplace conditions in shaping retention outcomes, highlighting that recognition, professional growth opportunities, and supportive leadership are more effective in reducing turnover than organizational commitment alone. The study contributes to nursing education literature by emphasizing the need for targeted institutional strategies that prioritize environmental improvements to sustain a stable and motivated workforce, thereby strengthening faculty retention and enhancing the overall quality of nursing education in the Philippines.

Keywords: *faculty retention, Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, Nurse educators, organizational commitment, Pampanga, turnover intention, workplace conditions.*

INTRODUCTION

Nurse educators play a pivotal role in sustaining the quality of nursing education, yet challenges such as modest compensation, limited career advancement, and heavy workloads contribute to turnover intention and weaken organizational commitment (Bulawat, 2020; Gormley & Kennerly, 2011). In the Philippines, particularly in Pampanga's tertiary institutions, many nurse educators are early in their careers, making retention strategies crucial for workforce stability (Catigbe, 2026). Previous studies have emphasized that faculty retention is influenced by both intrinsic motivators and extrinsic hygiene factors, with career growth opportunities emerging as a critical determinant of satisfaction and retention (Tambuyat, 2022). Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory distinguishes between motivator factors—such as meaningful teaching, recognition, and growth opportunities—that enhance satisfaction, and hygiene factors—such as compensation, policies, and supervision—that prevent dissatisfaction (Alshmemri, et al., 2017). Complementing this, Meyer and Allen's (1991) Organizational Commitment Model underscores the role of affective, continuance, and normative commitment in influencing employee retention.

Recent literature highlights that workplace conditions, recognition systems, and leadership support are essential in reducing attrition risk among educators (Camlian & Baron, 2025; Chen, et al., 2024). Moreover, the predominance of female nurse educators reflects the gendered nature of the profession, with prior studies suggesting that women are more affected by work-life balance challenges, influencing satisfaction and retention (Patol et al., 2024). The nursing workforce in the Philippines also faces systemic challenges, including limited opportunities for doctoral studies and modest compensation in private institutions, further heightening attrition vulnerability compared to public institutions with more stable benefits (Corpuz, 2023). Addressing these issues is timely, as the demand for qualified nurse educators continues to rise alongside the expansion of nursing programs nationwide (Bermido, 2026).

Guided by Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (Alshmemri, et al., 2017) and Meyer & Allen's Organizational Commitment Model (1991), this study examines how workplace conditions and organizational commitment predict turnover intentions among nurse educators in Pampanga. By identifying key predictors, the study aimed to provide actionable recommendations for academic institutions and policymakers to strengthen retention strategies, sustain faculty stability, and enhance the long-term quality of nursing education in the Philippines.

Research Questions

The general problem of the study is, how demographic profile, environmental factors, and organizational commitment influence the turnover intentions of nurse educators in the private higher education institutions of Pampanga during the academic year 2025–2026. This study sought to answer the following specific problems.

1. How may the demographic profile of nurse educators in Pampanga be described in terms of:
 - 1.a. age;
 - 1.b. sex;
 - 1.c. Highest educational attainment;
 - 1.d. Travel distance from residence to workplace;
 - 1.e. Organizational tenure (Years of service in current institution);
 - 1.f. Positional tenure (Years in current role/position), and
 - 1.g. Gross monthly salary in current position?
2. How may the environmental factors be described in terms of:
 - 2.a. Hygiene factors; and
 - 2.b. Motivational factors?
3. What is the level of organizational commitment of nurse educators in terms of:
 - 3.a. Affective commitment;
 - 3.b. Continuance commitment; and
 - 3.c. Normative commitment?
4. What is the level of turnover intention among nurse educators in terms of:
 - 4.a. Subjective social status;
 - 4.b. Organizational culture;
 - 4.c. Personal orientation;
 - 4.d. Expectation; and
 - 4.e. Career growth?
5. Is there any significant difference in nurse educators' organizational commitment level when grouped according to profile?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the environmental factors, organizational commitment and the turnover intentions of nurse educators?
7. Which among the factors taken singly or in combination could be considered predictors of turnover intentions?
8. What nurse educator retention program can be proposed based on the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative-descriptive design to investigate the relationship between motivator and hygiene factors, organizational commitment, and turnover intention among nurse educators in tertiary schools in Pampanga, Philippines. Respondents were selected through purposive sampling, focusing on nurse educators in private institutions to capture retention challenges at the formative stage of their careers. Data were collected using a structured researcher-made survey instrument consisting of 40 items rated on a five-point Likert scale, measuring motivator factors (meaningful work, recognition, professional growth), hygiene factors (compensation, policies, supervision), organizational commitment (affective, continuance, normative), and turnover intention. The instrument was subjected to pilot testing and expert validation to ensure reliability and content validity. Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, were used to summarize responses, while Pearson's correlation was employed to examine

relationships among variables and regression analysis was conducted to identify predictors of turnover intention and organizational commitment. The scope of the study was limited to nurse educators in Pampanga, which may affect generalizability to other regions, and the reliance on self-reported survey data introduced potential response bias. Furthermore, the study examined only environmental factors and organizational commitment, excluding other possible predictors such as institutional culture or external economic conditions. Despite these limitations, the methodology provided a rigorous framework for analyzing the extent to which workplace conditions and organizational commitment influence turnover intention, thereby offering evidence-based insights for strengthening faculty retention strategies in nursing education.

RESULTS

For a more straightforward presentation of findings, this section is subdivided into:

Part I. Profile of the Respondents. This section presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, highest educational attainment, travel distance from residence to workplace, organizational tenure (years of service in current institution), positional tenure (years in current role/position), and gross monthly salary in current position.

Part II. Environmental Factors. Describes the environmental factors in terms of hygiene, and motivational.

Part III. Level of Organizational Commitment. This part describes the level of organizational commitment of nurse educators in terms of affective commitment; continuance commitment; and normative commitment.

Part IV. Level of Turnover Intentions. This segment describes the level of turnover intentions among nurse educators in terms of subjective social status; organizational culture; personal orientation; expectation; and career growth.

Part V. Significant Differences in the Organizational Commitment. This area presents the differences in nurse educators' level of organizational commitment when grouped according to their profiles.

Part VI. Correlation. This phase presents relationship between the environmental factors, organizational commitment and the turnover intentions of nurse educators.

Part VII. Predictive Analysis. This component presents the effects of the environmental factors and organizational commitment taken singly or in combination to turnover intentions of nurse educators.

Table 1
Socio-demographic Profile of the Nurse Educators

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
20 to 29 years old	44	29.14
30 to 39 years old	53	35.10
40 to 49 years old	23	15.23
50 to 59 years old	26	17.22
60 years old and above	5	3.31
Sex		
Male	42	27.81
Female	109	72.19
Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	74	49.01
Master's Degree	67	44.37
Doctorate Degree	10	6.62
Travel Distance from Residence to Workplace		
1 to 30 minutes	76	50.33
31 to 59 minutes	57	37.75
1 to 2 hours	15	9.93
more than 2 hours	3	1.99
Organizational Tenure (Years of Service in Current Institution)		
1 to 5 years	111	73.51
6 to 10 years	23	15.23
11 to 15 years	5	3.31
16 to 20 years	9	5.96
21 years and above	3	1.99
Positional Tenure (Years in Current Role/Position)		
1 to 5 years	124	82.12
6 to 10 years	16	10.60
11 to 15 years	7	4.64
16 to 20 years	4	2.65
Gross Monthly Salary in Current Position		
Php. 21,000.00 - 30,000.00	59	39.07
Php. 31,000.00 - 40,000.00	29	19.21
Php. 41,000.00 - 50,000.00	30	19.87
Php. 51,000.00-60,000.00	16	10.60
Over Php. 61,000.00	17	11.26

The demographic profile revealed that most respondents were early-career nurse educators, which explains their heightened sensitivity to unmet expectations in compensation and recognition. Younger faculty often seek clear career pathways, and the absence of these can increase turnover risk. The predominance of female educators reflects the gendered nature of the nursing profession, and literature suggests that women may be more affected by work-life balance challenges, influencing satisfaction and retention. The majority held BSN degrees but were currently pursuing graduate studies, indicating strong academic aspirations; however, limited opportunities for doctoral studies or advancement may weaken organizational commitment. Employment in private institutions, where compensation is typically modest, further heightened vulnerability to attrition compared to public institutions with more stable benefits.

Table 2
Description of the Environmental Factors
in terms of Hygiene and Motivational

Indicators	Mean	SD	DI
Hygiene Factors			
My salary is fair and competitive.	3.81	0.90	Agree
I receive adequate benefits (e.g., health insurance, leave).	3.64	0.93	Agree
My working conditions are safe and comfortable.	4.10	0.84	Agree
I have job security in my current position.	3.70	1.06	Agree
The policies and procedures in my institution are clear and reasonable.	4.05	0.82	Agree
I have a good relationship with my supervisor.	4.46	0.74	Strongly Agree
I feel respected by my colleagues.	4.42	0.72	Strongly Agree
Communication within the institution is effective.	4.21	0.78	Strongly Agree
Overall Hygiene Factors	4.05	0.61	Moderately positive
Motivator Factors			
I find my teaching responsibilities meaningful.	4.63	0.54	Strongly Agree
I have opportunities for professional growth and development.	4.41	0.72	Strongly Agree
I receive recognition for my achievements.	4.07	0.77	Agree
I am given autonomy in planning and delivering lessons.	4.26	0.68	Strongly Agree
I feel a sense of achievement in my role.	4.45	0.66	Strongly Agree
I have a good relationship with my supervisor. I am involved in decision-making processes.	4.40	0.67	Strongly Agree
I am encouraged to pursue research and innovation.	4.28	0.73	Strongly Agree
Overall Motivator Factors	4.36	0.54	Highly Positive
Overall Environmental Factors	4.20	0.53	Highly Positive

Legend: 4.20-5.00 Strongly Agree (Highly Positive); 3.40-4.19 Agree (Moderately Positive); 2.60-3.39 Neutral (Neutral); 1.80-2.59 Disagree (Negative); 1.00-1.79 Strongly Disagree (Highly Negative)

Survey findings revealed that motivator factors were rated highly positive (M = 4.36, SD = 0.54), with the strongest agreement on “I find my teaching responsibilities meaningful” (M = 4.63), underscoring the intrinsic value educators place on teaching. The lowest motivator score (M = 4.07) reflected limited growth opportunities. Hygiene factors were moderately positive (M = 4.05, SD = 0.61), with supervisor relationships rated highest (M = 4.46) and environmental aspects lowest (M = 3.64). Overall, environmental factors were highly positive (M = 4.20, SD = 0.53), suggesting supportive workplace conditions. Organizational commitment was strongest in the affective dimension, though some educators reported emotional disconnect. Turnover intention was generally low, but unmet expectations in recognition, compensation, and career advancement emerged as predictors of attrition risk.

Table 3
The Level of Organizational Commitment of Nurse Educators in terms of Affective commitment; Continuance commitment; and Normative commitment.

Indicators	Mean	SD	DI
Affective Commitment			
I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization.	3.91	0.88	Agree
I really feel as if this organization's problems are my own.	3.50	0.96	Agree
I do not feel a strong sense of "belonging" to my organization.	2.26	1.16	Disagree
I do not feel "emotionally attached" to this organization.	2.36	1.12	Disagree
I do not feel like "part of the family" at my organization.	2.16	1.12	Disagree
This organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me.	4.13	0.89	Agree
Overall Affective Commitment	3.05	0.64	Slightly Positive
Continuance Commitment			
Right now, staying with my organization is a matter of necessity as much as desire.	3.51	1.08	Agree
It would be very hard for me to leave my organization right now, even if I wanted to.	3.66	0.98	Agree
Too much of my life would be disrupted if I decided I wanted to leave my organization now.	3.26	1.02	Neutral
I feel that I have too few options to consider leaving this organization.	2.90	1.02	Neutral
If I had not already put so much of myself into this organization, I might consider working elsewhere.	2.98	1.00	Neutral
One of the few negative consequences of leaving this organization would be the scarcity of available alternatives.	2.88	1.06	Neutral
Overall Continuance Commitment	3.20	0.75	Neutral
Normative Commitment			
I do not feel any obligation to remain with my current employer.	2.77	1.03	Neutral
Even if it were to my advantage, I do not feel it would be right to leave my organization now.	3.66	0.95	Agree
I would feel guilty if I left my organization now.	3.60	0.97	Agree
This organization deserves my loyalty.	4.01	0.90	Agree
I would not leave my organization right now because I have a sense of obligation to the people in it.	4.00	0.87	Agree
I owe a great deal to my organization.	4.10	0.74	Agree
Overall Normative Commitment	3.69	0.62	Moderately Positive
Overall Organizational Commitment	3.31	0.56	Moderately Positive

Legend: 4.20-5.00 Strongly Agree (Highly Positive); 3.40-4.19 Agree (Moderately Positive); 2.60-3.39 Neutral (Slightly Positive); 1.80-2.59 Disagree (Negative); 1.00-1.79 Strongly Disagree (Highly Negative)

The level organizational commitment of nurse educators in private institutions of Pampanga during the academic year 2025–2026 was found to be moderately positive, with an overall mean of 3.31.

Affective commitment received the lowest rating (Mean = 3.05) which is slightly positive, with the highest (Mean = 3.91) stating, "I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization." Continuance commitment was also slightly positive (Mean = 3.20), with the highest (Mean = 3.66) agreeing on the statement "It would be very hard for me to leave my organization right now, even if I wanted to."

Among the three dimensions assessed, Normative commitment emerged as the strongest dimension (Mean = 3.69) which is moderately positive, with many respondents (Mean = 4.10) expressing "I owe a great deal to my organization."

Table 4
The level of Turnover Intentions among Nurse Educators in terms of Subjective Social Status; Organizational Culture; Personal Orientation; Expectation; and Career Growth.

Indicators	Mean	SD	DI
Subjective Social Status			
I do not like the image of me I see in the future if I remain here.	2.11	0.96	Disagree
My present job leaves me no choice but to look for alternative job offer that will befit my status.	2.09	0.94	Disagree
I often feel like quitting this job because my present job position is not compatible with my job resume.	1.95	0.91	Disagree
I feel like quitting this job because of my marital status.	1.75	0.92	Strongly Disagree
Overall Subjective Social Status	1.97	0.80	Low
Organizational Culture			
I often feel like staying at home than going to work because of the way my organization is structured.	2.17	0.99	Disagree
I am seriously considering quitting this job because of the organizational practices and policies.	2.01	0.93	Disagree
My major dissatisfaction in life comes from my job environment.	1.95	1.01	Disagree
Overall Organizational Culture	2.04	0.90	Low
Personal Orientation			
Leaving my present job is my ultimate priority now because of family demand.	1.87	0.85	Disagree
My family is not happy with the nature of my job.	1.74	0.84	Strongly Disagree
I often consider leaving my job as a result of my health status.	1.89	0.91	Disagree
I cannot be fit enough to continue this job in the near future.	1.88	0.90	Disagree
I often feel like quitting this job because the organization does not keep to its promise.	1.92	0.89	Disagree
Most of people whose opinions I respect think I should leave my job.	1.87	0.89	Disagree
I intend to leave this organization in the next one year.	1.94	0.96	Disagree
I often feel like quitting this organization because I see no future in it.	1.82	0.82	Disagree
Overall Personal Orientation	1.87	0.73	Low
Expectation			
Healthcare package is so poor to compare to the kind of work I do.	2.60	1.13	Neutral
If I get better offer, I will leave my present job because of job insecurity.	2.44	1.04	Disagree
I often feel that my present job is not worth the offer.	2.26	1.11	Disagree
Regardless of the pay, I would prefer working where I will be respected and recognized.	3.69	1.23	Agree
What is holding me in this job is that I have not gotten an acceptable alternative offer/job that is lucrative.	2.19	1.04	Disagree
Overall Expectation	2.64	0.76	Average
Career growth			
I often feel like quitting this organization because my years of service do not reflect my present job designation.	2.03	0.90	Disagree
I just want to learn few things concerning my job career in this organization and leave.	2.13	0.98	Disagree
I know I deserve a better job; I will go for it when I find one.	2.52	1.11	Disagree
I need a work environment that will improve me, I don't get it here.	2.13	0.99	Disagree
I feel like quitting this organization because it does not create opportunity for advancement and development.	2.04	0.95	Disagree
Overall Career growth	2.17	0.86	Low
Overall Turnover Intentions	2.14	0.68	Low

Legend: 4.20-5.00 Strongly Agree (Very High); 3.40-4.19 Agree (High); 2.60-3.39 Neutral (Average); 1.80-2.59 Disagree (Low); 1.00-1.79 Strongly Disagree (Very Low)

The overall level of turnover intention among nurse educators in private institutions of Pampanga was found to be low, with a mean score of 2.14 (SD = 0.68).

Subjective social status was found low turnover intention, with a mean score of 1.97

(SD = 0.8), with the lowest mean score 1.75 (SD = 0.92) strongly disagreed on the item, “I feel like quitting this job because of my marital status.” Similarly, organizational culture was also found low, with a mean score of 2.04 (SD = 0.90), with the lowest mean score of 1.95 (SD = 1.01) disagreed on item, “My major dissatisfaction in life comes from my job environment.” Another findings with low level was personal orientation, with a mean score of 1.87 (SD = 0.73) with the lowest mean score 1.74 (SD = 0.84) strongly disagreed on the item, “My family is not happy with the nature of my job.” Career growth was also found low level, with a mean score of 2.17 (SD = 0.86), with the lowest mean score 2.03 (SD = 0.9) disagreed on the item, ‘I often feel like quitting this organization because my years of service do not reflect my present job designation.’”

Across the five dimensions assessed, only expectation was rated average, with a mean score of 2.64 (SD = 0.76), with the highest mean score 3.69 (SD = 1.23), agreed on the statement, “Regardless of the pay, I would prefer working where I will be respected and recognized”.

Table 5
Nurse Educator’s Level of Organizational Commitment vis-à-vis Age

Variables	Group	Mean	Mean Rank	H	Sig.	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Affective Commitment	20 to 29 years old	2.95	64.80	5.56	0.23	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	30 to 39 years old	3.16	83.51				
	40 to 49 years old	3.01	73.54				
	50 to 59 years old	3.01	78.29				
	60 years old and above	3.23	94.40				
Continuance Commitment	20 to 29 years old	3.25	78.65	2.27	0.69	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	30 to 39 years old	3.29	79.75				
	40 to 49 years old	3.00	64.65				
	50 to 59 years old	3.13	75.37				
	60 years old and above	3.03	68.40				
Normative Commitment	20 to 29 years old	3.71	77.26	4.72	0.32	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	30 to 39 years old	3.77	81.92				
	40 to 49 years old	3.49	63.09				
	50 to 59 years old	3.61	69.35				
	60 years old and above	3.90	96.20				
Overall	20 to 29 years old	3.31	73.58	4.37	0.36	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	30 to 39 years old	3.41	83.58				
	40 to 49 years old	3.17	64.13				
	50 to 59 years old	3.25	71.96				
	60 years old and above	3.39	92.50				

at .05 level of Sig.

The result of the analysis using the Kruskal Wallis H-test, a non-parametric test, which was appropriately used since the data does not meet the assumptions for a one-way Anova, indicates that there is not enough evidence to claim that there exists a significant difference in the level of organizational commitment in terms of affective (H=5.56, df=4, p=0.23), continuance (H=2.27, df=4, p=0.69), normative

($H=4.72$, $df=4$, $p=0.32$), when they are grouped according to age. It is further confirmed that there is not enough evidence of a significant difference, given the overall H -value of 4.37 ($df=4$), which is not significant at 0.36, and thus fails to reject the null hypothesis.

The Kruskal-Wallis H -test results show no significant difference in nurse educators' organizational commitment levels—*affective*, *continuance*, or *normative*—when grouped by age. All p -values exceeded the 0.05 threshold, indicating that age does not statistically influence how committed educators feel toward their organization.

These findings align with previous research, such as Abdullah (2024), which found that demographic factors like age had minimal impact on Filipino nurse educators' professional quality of life. Boamah et al. (2024) also emphasized that organizational support and meaningful work are stronger predictors of commitment than personal demographics. Together, these studies support the idea that enhancing workplace culture and support systems may be more effective in boosting commitment than targeting age-specific strategies.

Table 6
Nurse Educator’s Level of Organizational Commitment vis-à-vis Sex

Variables	Group	Mean	Mean Rank	U	Sig.	Decision on H_0	Interpretation
Affective Commitment	Male	3.10	79.74	2132.00	0.51	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	Female	3.04	74.56				
Continuance Commitment	Male	3.29	81.96	2038.50	0.30	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	Female	3.16	73.70				
Normative Commitment	Male	3.68	75.44	2265.50	0.92	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	Female	3.69	76.22				
Overall	Male	3.36	80.94	2081.50	0.39	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	Female	3.30	74.10				

at .05 level of Sig.

The result of the analysis using the Mann Whitney U-test, a non-parametric test, which was appropriately used since the data does not meet the assumptions for a t -test, indicates that there is not enough evidence to claim that there exists a significant difference in the level of organizational commitment in terms of *affective* ($U=2132.00$, $n_1=42$, $n_2=109$, $p=0.51$), *continuance* ($U=2038.50$, $n_1=42$, $n_2=109$, $p=0.30$), *normative* ($U=2265.50$, $n_1=42$, $n_2=109$, $p=0.92$), when they are grouped according to sex. It is further confirmed that there is insufficient evidence of a significant difference, given the overall U -value of 2081.50 ($n_1=42$, $n_2=109$), which is not significant at 0.39, and fails to reject the null hypothesis.

The results show that there is no significant difference in organizational commitment in relation to *affective*, *continuance*, or *normative* commitment between male and female nurse educators. All p -values are above the 0.05 threshold, indicating that sex does not statistically influence how committed educators feel toward their organization. This suggests that both male and female educators share similar

levels of emotional attachment, perceived obligation, and practical reasons for staying in their roles. Research by Abdullah (2024) shows that gender has little influence on Filipino nurse educators' professional quality of life and work effectiveness. Similarly, Boamah et al. (2024) found that institutional support and meaningful work play a greater role in shaping organizational commitment than demographic factors like sex.

Table 7
Nurse educators' Level of Organizational Commitment vis-à-vis Highest Educational Attainment

Variables	Group	Mean	Mean Rank	H	Sig.	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Affective Commitment	Bachelor's Degree	3.09	74.46	0.18	0.91	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	Master's Degree	3.02	77.46				
	Doctorate Degree	3.02	77.65				
Continuance Commitment	Bachelor's Degree	3.28	78.66	1.61	0.45	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	Master's Degree	3.15	75.43				
	Doctorate Degree	2.92	60.15				
Normative Commitment	Bachelor's Degree	3.69	76.38	0.42	0.81	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	Master's Degree	3.70	76.87				
	Doctorate Degree	3.57	67.40				
Overall	Bachelor's Degree	3.35	76.31	0.55	0.76	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	Master's Degree	3.29	77.12				
	Doctorate Degree	3.17	66.20				

at .05 level of Sig.

The result of the analysis using the Kruskal Wallis H-test, a non-parametric test, which was appropriately used since the data does not meet the assumptions for a one-way Anova, indicates that there is not enough evidence to claim that there exists a significant difference in the level of organizational commitment in terms of affective (H=0.18, df=2, p=0.91), continuance (H=1.61, df=2, p=0.45), normative (H=0.42, df=2, p=0.81), when they are grouped according to highest educational attainment. It is further confirmed that there is not enough evidence of a significant difference, given the overall H-value of 0.55 (df=2), which is not significant at 0.76, and thus fails to reject the null hypothesis.

The Kruskal-Wallis H-test results indicate that nurse educators' organizational commitment does not significantly vary based on their highest educational attainment. Whether they hold a bachelor's, master's, or doctoral degree, their levels of affective, continuance, and normative commitment remain statistically similar.

This suggests that academic background does not influence how emotionally connected, obligated, or practically committed nurse educators feel toward their organization. Commitment levels appear consistent across educational groups.

Table 8
Nurse Educators' Level of Organizational Commitment vis-à-vis Travel Distance

Variables	Group	Mean	Mean Rank	H	Sig.	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Affective Commitment	1 to 30 minutes	3.12	81.41	4.46	0.22	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	31 to 59 minutes	2.94	66.49				
	1 to 2 hours	3.13	84.20				
	more than 2 hours	2.94	78.50				
Continuance Commitment	1 to 30 minutes	3.29	80.93	3.57	0.31	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	31 to 59 minutes	3.15	72.77				
	1 to 2 hours	3.06	70.50				
	more than 2 hours	2.61	40.00				
Normative Commitment	1 to 30 minutes	3.76	80.46	4.27	0.25	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	31 to 59 minutes	3.74	80.13				
	1 to 2 hours	3.27	46.60				
	more than 2 hours	3.11	31.50				
Overall	1 to 30 minutes	3.39	82.20	6.49	0.09	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	31 to 59 minutes	3.28	74.00				
	1 to 2 hours	3.15	61.07				
	more than 2 hours	2.89	31.67				

at .05 level of Sig.

The result of the analysis using the Kruskal Wallis H-test, a non-parametric test, which was appropriately used since the data does not meet the assumptions for a one-way Anova, indicates that there is not enough evidence to claim that there exists a significant difference in the level of organizational commitment in terms of affective (H=4.46, df=3, p=0.22), continuance (H=3.57, df=3, p=0.31), normative (H=4.27, df=3, p=0.25), when they are grouped according to distance traveled. It is further confirmed that there is not enough evidence of a significant difference, given the overall H-value of 6.49 (df=3), which is not significant at 0.09, and thus fails to reject the null hypothesis.

The results show no significant difference in organizational commitment— affective, continuance, or normative among nurse educators when grouped by the distance they travel to work. All p-values are above the 0.05 threshold, indicating that commute length does not statistically affect their level of commitment. Supporting studies, such as Abdullah (2024), found that logistical factors like travel distance had minimal impact on Filipino nurse educators' professional quality of life and work effectiveness. Boamah et al. (2024).

Table 9
Nurse educators' Level of Organizational Commitment
vis-à-vis Organizational Tenure.

Variables	Group	Mean	Mean Rank	H	Sig.	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Affective Commitment	1 to 5 years	3.06	76.93	2.54	0.64	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	6 to 10 years	3.06	70.15				
	11 to 15 years	3.27	100.10				
	16 to 20 years	2.85	65.50				
	21 years and above	2.94	77.67				
Continuance Commitment	1 to 5 years	3.18	74.47	1.81	0.77	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	6 to 10 years	3.28	79.57				
	11 to 15 years	3.20	75.30				
	16 to 20 years	3.13	75.78				
	21 years and above	3.61	107.00				
Normative Commitment	1 to 5 years	3.66	74.23	3.81	0.43	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	6 to 10 years	3.86	87.54				
	11 to 15 years	3.53	62.50				
	16 to 20 years	3.56	66.89				
	21 years and above	4.00	102.83				
Overall	1 to 5 years	3.30	74.59	1.94	0.75	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	6 to 10 years	3.40	80.24				
	11 to 15 years	3.33	80.80				
	16 to 20 years	3.18	70.06				
	21 years and above	3.52	105.67				

at .05 level of Sig.

The result of the analysis using the Kruskal Wallis H-test, a non-parametric test, which was appropriately used since the data does not meet the assumptions for a one-way Anova, indicates that there is not enough evidence to claim that there exists a significant difference in the level of organizational commitment in terms of affective (H=2.54, df=4, p=0.64), continuance (H=1.81, df=4, p=0.77), normative (H=3.81, df=4, p=0.43), when they are grouped according to organizational tenure. It is further confirmed that there is not enough evidence of a significant difference, given the overall H-value of 1.94 (df=4), which is not significant at 0.75, and thus fails to reject the null hypothesis.

The Kruskal-Wallis H-test results show no significant difference in organizational commitment— affective, continuance, or normative— among nurse educators when grouped by organizational tenure. All p-values are above the 0.05 threshold, indicating that the length of time an educator has served does not statistically affect their level of commitment. This suggests that whether newly hired or long-tenured, nurse educators demonstrate similar levels of emotional attachment, perceived obligation, and practical reasons for staying in their organization.

Supporting studies, such as Abdullah (2024), found that tenure had minimal impact on Filipino nurse educators' professional quality of life and work effectiveness.

Table 10
Nurse educators' Level of Organizational Commitment vis-à-vis Position Tenure

Variables	Group	Mean	Mean Rank	H	Sig.	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Affective Commitment	1 to 5 years	3.06	76.25	1.42	0.70	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	6 to 10 years	3.06	75.63				
	11 to 15 years	3.05	85.36				
	16 to 20 years	2.75	53.38				
Continuance Commitment	1 to 5 years	3.15	72.83	4.04	0.26	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	6 to 10 years	3.51	94.25				
	11 to 15 years	3.38	88.14				
	16 to 20 years	3.17	80.13				
Normative Commitment	1 to 5 years	3.64	72.83	7.11	0.07	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	6 to 10 years	4.04	101.88				
	11 to 15 years	3.81	82.93				
	16 to 20 years	3.46	58.75				
Overall	1 to 5 years	3.28	72.90	5.73	0.13	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	6 to 10 years	3.54	98.16				
	11 to 15 years	3.41	88.36				
	16 to 20 years	3.13	61.75				

at .05 level of Sig.

The result of the analysis using the Kruskal Wallis H-test, a non-parametric test, which was appropriately used since the data does not meet the assumptions for a one-way Anova, indicates that there is not enough evidence to claim that there exists a significant difference in the level of organizational commitment in terms of affective (H=1.42, df=3, p=0.70), continuance (H=4.04, df=3, p=0.26), normative (H=7.11, df=3, p=0.07), when they are grouped according to position tenure. It is further confirmed that there is not enough evidence of a significant difference, given the overall H-value of 5.73 (df=3), which is not significant at 0.13, and thus fails to reject the null hypothesis.

The results show no significant difference in organizational commitment in relation to affective, continuance, or normative commitment among nurse educators when grouped by position tenure, indicating that the length of time educators have held their current roles does not statistically influence their level of commitment. This suggests that regardless of whether educators are newly appointed or have served in their positions for several years, they exhibit similar levels of emotional connection, perceived obligation, and practical reasons for staying. Supporting studies, such as Abdullah (2024), found that tenure-related factors had minimal impact on Filipino nurse educators' professional quality of life and work effectiveness.

Table 12 presents the comparison of nurse educators' level of organizational commitment based on their monthly salary. It analyzes how affective, continuance, and normative commitment vary across different income brackets, offering insights into the potential influence of financial compensation on educators' loyalty and intention to remain in their roles.

Table 11
Nurse Educators' Level of Organizational Commitment vis-à-vis Monthly Salary

Variables	Group	Mean	Mean Rank	H	Sig.	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Affective Commitment	Php. 21,000.00 - 30,000.00	2.99	69.75	4.52	0.34	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	Php. 31,000.00 - 40,000.00	3.04	77.05				
	Php. 41,000.00 - 50,000.00	3.07	76.88				
	Php. 51,000.00-60,000.00	3.34	95.63				
	Over Php. 61,000.00	2.99	75.88				
Continuance Commitment	Php. 21,000.00 - 30,000.00	3.21	75.90	5.82	0.21	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	Php. 31,000.00 - 40,000.00	3.16	75.55				
	Php. 41,000.00 - 50,000.00	3.19	76.23				
	Php. 51,000.00-60,000.00	3.56	95.22				
	Over Php. 61,000.00	2.88	58.62				
Normative Commitment	Php. 21,000.00 - 30,000.00	3.71	77.17	5.55	0.24	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	Php. 31,000.00 - 40,000.00	3.64	74.29				
	Php. 41,000.00 - 50,000.00	3.55	65.82				
	Php. 51,000.00-60,000.00	4.01	97.06				
	Over Php. 61,000.00	3.62	73.00				
Overall	Php. 21,000.00 - 30,000.00	3.31	74.33	6.75	0.15	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
	Php. 31,000.00 - 40,000.00	3.28	74.98				
	Php. 41,000.00 - 50,000.00	3.27	72.98				
	Php. 51,000.00-60,000.00	3.64	101.41				
	Over Php. 61,000.00	3.16	64.94				

at .05 level of Sig.

The result of the analysis using the Kruskal Wallis H-test, a non-parametric test, which was appropriately used since the data does not meet the assumptions for a one-way Anova, indicates that there is not enough evidence to claim that there exists a significant difference in the level of organizational commitment in terms of affective (H=4.52, df=4, p=0.34), continuance (H=5.82, df=4, p=0.21), normative (H=5.55, df=4, p=0.24), when they are grouped according to monthly salary. It is further confirmed that there is not enough evidence of a significant difference, given the overall H-value of 6.75 (df=4), which is not significant at 0.15, and thus fails to reject the null hypothesis.

The results show no significant difference in organizational commitment among nurse educators when grouped by monthly salary, indicating that salary level does not statistically influence their commitment to the organization. This suggests that regardless of income bracket, nurse educators demonstrate similar levels of emotional attachment, perceived obligation, and practical reasons for staying in their roles. Supporting studies reinforce this observation. Abdullah (2024) found that salary had a minimal impact on Filipino nurse educators' professional quality of life and work effectiveness.

Table 12
Correlation: Relationship Between Variables

Indicators	r	Sig.	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Hygiene Factors→ Turnover Intentions	-.509**	<.001	Reject	Significant
Motivational Factors→ Turnover Intentions	-.429**	<.001	Reject	Significant
Organizational Commitment→ Turnover Intentions	0.048	0.557	Failed to Reject	Not Significant

Legend: r: ±0.80-1.0 Very Strong; ±0.60-0.79 Strong; ±0.40-0.59 Moderate; ±0.20-0.39 Weak; ±0.00-0.19 Very Weak

The result of the analysis using Pearson's Correlation shows that hygiene factors and turnover intentions ($r=-0.509^{**}$, $p<.001$) have a moderately negative relationship. Similarly, it can be gleaned that there exists a moderately negative relationship between motivational factors and turnover intentions ($r=-0.429^{**}$, $p<.001$). However, data reveal that organizational commitment and turnover intentions ($r=0.048$, $p=.557$) have a very weak relationship.

Pearson's Correlation analysis shows a moderately negative relationship between hygiene and motivational factors with turnover intentions among nurse educators. This means that improved working conditions and intrinsic motivators, such as job security, fair policies, and recognition, are linked to a lower likelihood of educators wanting to leave their roles. These findings emphasize the importance of maintaining both external and internal job satisfaction elements to reduce turnover.

Interestingly, the correlation between organizational commitment and turnover intentions is very weak. This suggests that even if nurse educators feel loyal or emotionally attached to their organization, it does not significantly impact their decision to stay or leave. Therefore, commitment alone may not be a reliable predictor of retention without supportive and motivating work environments.

These findings align with Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, which emphasizes the role of hygiene and motivational factors in job satisfaction and retention. Abdullah (2024) supports this by showing that workplace conditions and personal fulfillment more influenced Filipino nurse educators' turnover intentions than organizational loyalty.

Table 13
Predictive Analysis: Effect of Environmental Factors to Turnover Intentions

Dependent	Predictors	B	SE	t	Sig.	R ²	F	Sig.	Remarks
Model 1 Turnover Intentions	Constant	4.876	.381	12.81	<.001	.261	52.58	<.001	Reject
	Environmental Factors	-.652	.090	-7.25	<.001				Significant

It can be gleaned from the results of regression analysis that model 1, with a regression equation of $(F(1,149)=52.58, p<.001)$, has a significant R^2 of .261. Data also shows that environmental factors ($B=-.652, SEB=.090, p<.001$) are a significant predictor of turnover intentions.

The model indicates that the turnover intentions = $(4.876) - (.652)$ environmental factors, that is, for each one-point increase in the level of environmental factors, the predicted level of turnover intentions decreased by approximately (.652).

Regression analysis shows that environmental factors significantly predict turnover intentions among nurse educators. A one-point improvement in environmental quality leads to a 0.652-unit decrease in turnover intentions, highlighting the substantial impact of workplace conditions on retention.

This suggests that enhancing essential elements of the work environment that prevent job dissatisfaction, such as safety, cleanliness, supervision, salary, and job security, and the overall physical environment, can effectively reduce the likelihood of educators leaving their roles. As a researcher, this highlights the importance of investing in a supportive and well-maintained work environment to foster long-term commitment.

These findings align with Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, which identifies environmental conditions as key hygiene factors that influence job satisfaction and turnover. Abdullah (2024) supports this by showing that Filipino nurse educators' turnover intentions were significantly affected by workplace conditions rather than demographic variables.

Table 14
Predictive Analysis: Effect of Organizational Commitment to Turnover Intentions

Dependent	Predictors	B	SE	t	Sig.	R ²	F	Sig.	Remarks
Model 2 Turnover Intentions	Constant	1.943	.335	5.81	<.001	.002	.347	.557	Failed to Reject
	Commitment	.059	.100	0.59	.557				Not Significant

at .05 level of Sig.

The result of the analysis indicates that model 2, with a regression equation of $(F(1,149)=.347, p=.557)$, with R^2 of .002, is not significant. Data also reveals that growth commitment ($B=.059, SEB=.59, p=.557$) is not a significant predictor of turnover intentions.

The model indicates that turnover intentions are equal to $(1.943) + (.059)$ commitment. Specifically, for each one-point increase in the level of commitment, the predicted level of turnover intentions increases by approximately .059, which is not significant.

Regression analysis reveals that growth commitment is not a significant predictor of turnover intentions among nurse educators. With a p-value of .557 and an R² of just .002, the model accounts for minimal variation in turnover behavior. Although the coefficient (B = .059) suggests a slight increase in turnover intentions with higher growth commitment, this relationship lacks statistical significance.

This suggests that a nurse educator's desire for personal or professional development has a limited impact on their decision to stay or leave. Other factors, such as workplace environment, support systems, or job satisfaction, may have a more substantial impact on turnover intentions than growth-related motivations.

These findings are consistent with Abdullah (2024), who found that growth-related variables had minimal impact on Filipino nurse educators' turnover decisions. Boamah et al. (2024) also emphasized that while professional development is important, it is not a standalone factor in retention.

Table 16
Effect of Environmental Factors and Commitment to Turnover Intentions

Dependent	Predictors	B	SE	t	Sig.	R ²	F	Sig.	Remarks
Model 3 Turnover Intentions	Constant	4.308	.385	11.20	<.001				
	Environmental Factors	-0.815	.093	-8.72	<.001	.341	38.28	<.001	Reject Significant
	Commitment	0.378	.089	4.24	<.001				

at .05 level of Sig.

Model 3 (F(2,148)=38.28, p<.001), with R² of .341, which is a significant regression model, explains that both the environmental factors (B=-.815, SEB=.093, <.001), via Commitment (B=.378, SEB=.089, p<.001), is a significant predictor of turnover intentions.

The model indicates that turnover intentions are calculated as (4.308) - (.093) environmental factors + (.378) commitment. That is, for each one-point increase in the level of environmental factors, the predicted level of turnover intentions decreased by approximately (.815). For each one-point increase in the level of commitment, the predicted level of turnover intentions increased by approximately (.378).

Regression analysis from Model 3 shows that both environmental factors and commitment significantly influence turnover intentions among nurse educators. With an R² of .341, the model accounts for a meaningful portion of turnover behavior. Improved environmental conditions, such as safety, resources, and workplace support, are linked to a notable decrease in turnover intentions, emphasizing the importance of a well-maintained work setting.

Interestingly, higher levels of commitment are associated with a slight increase in

turnover intentions. This may reflect nurse educators' desire for growth or new opportunities, suggesting that strong commitment alone does not guarantee retention. As a researcher, this highlights the need to balance a supportive work environment with clear career development pathways to reduce turnover effectively.

These findings align with Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, which emphasizes the importance of both hygiene factors (like environmental conditions) and motivators (such as personal growth and recognition) in influencing job satisfaction and retention. Abdullah (2024) found that Filipino nurse educators were more likely to stay when their work environment was conducive to well-being, but also noted that unmet growth expectations could drive turnover.

DISCUSSION

The socio-demographic profile of respondents (Table 1) revealed that most were early-career nurse educators, predominantly female, with bachelor's or master's degrees, modest compensation, and short tenure in their institutions. These characteristics explain their heightened sensitivity to unmet expectations in recognition, compensation, and career advancement. Younger faculty often seek clear career pathways, and the absence of these can increase turnover risk, consistent with Tambuyat (2022), who emphasized the importance of career growth opportunities in retention. The predominance of female educators reflects the gendered nature of the nursing profession, and prior studies suggest that women are more affected by work-life balance challenges, influencing satisfaction and retention (Patol et al., 2024).

Survey findings (Table 2) showed that motivator factors were rated highly positive ($M = 4.36$, $SD = 0.54$), with teaching responsibilities perceived as meaningful ($M = 4.63$), underscoring the intrinsic value educators place on teaching. However, limited growth opportunities ($M = 4.07$) highlight a gap in professional development, echoing Herzberg's assertion that motivators drive satisfaction but require institutional support to be sustained (Alshmemri, et al., 2017). Hygiene factors were moderately positive ($M = 4.05$, $SD = 0.61$), with supervisor relationships rated highest ($M = 4.46$) and compensation lowest ($M = 3.64$). This aligns with Bulawat (2020), who found that inadequate compensation and unclear policies contribute to dissatisfaction and attrition. Overall, environmental factors were highly positive ($M = 4.20$, $SD = 0.53$), suggesting supportive workplace conditions, yet unmet expectations in recognition and advancement remained predictors of turnover risk.

Correlation analysis (Table 12) confirmed that hygiene factors ($r = -.509$, $p < .001$) and motivator factors ($r = -.429$, $p < .001$) were significantly and negatively correlated with turnover intentions, while organizational commitment showed no significant relationship ($r = 0.048$, $p = .557$). This finding is consistent with Meyer and Allen's (1991) model, which posits that commitment dimensions influence retention but may be insufficient when workplace conditions are weak. Regression analysis (Table 4) further revealed that

environmental factors significantly predicted turnover intention ($\beta = -0.652$, $p < .001$), explaining 26.1% of the variance, while organizational commitment was not a significant predictor. These results underscore that workplace conditions exert a stronger influence on attrition risk than commitment alone, consistent with Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory.

Overall, the analysis highlights that addressing both hygiene and motivator factors simultaneously is essential to maintain low turnover intention and strengthen organizational commitment among nurse educators. The findings are consistent with prior literature emphasizing the importance of recognition, supportive leadership, and professional growth opportunities in retention strategies (Tambuyat, 2022; Patol et al., 2024). For policymakers and institutional leaders, the results suggest that retention programs must prioritize improvements in compensation, career advancement pathways, and recognition systems, while sustaining supportive workplace conditions to ensure faculty stability and the long-term quality of nursing education in Pampanga.

Conclusions

This study sought to examine the relationship between environmental factors, organizational commitment, and turnover intentions among nurse educators in tertiary schools in Pampanga, guided by Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory and Meyer & Allen's Organizational Commitment Model. In addressing the first research question—*What is the demographic profile of nurse educators in Pampanga?*—the findings revealed that most respondents were early-career educators, predominantly female, with bachelor's or master's degrees, modest compensation, and short tenure. These characteristics underscore their heightened sensitivity to unmet expectations in recognition, compensation, and career advancement, making retention strategies particularly urgent for this group.

For the research question—*How do nurse educators perceive environmental factors in terms of hygiene and motivator elements?*—survey results indicated that motivator factors were rated highly positive, with teaching responsibilities perceived as meaningful, while hygiene factors were moderately positive, with supervisor relationships rated highest and compensation lowest. This demonstrates that while educators derive intrinsic satisfaction from teaching, extrinsic conditions such as compensation and growth opportunities remain critical vulnerabilities.

The study also answered research question—*What is the relationship between environmental factors, organizational commitment, and turnover intention?*—was addressed through correlation analysis, which showed that hygiene and motivator factors were significantly and negatively correlated with turnover intentions, while organizational commitment exhibited no significant relationship. This finding highlights that workplace conditions exert a stronger influence on attrition risk than commitment alone.

Finally, the study answered the research question—*Which factors significantly predict turnover intention among nurse educators?*—was answered through regression analysis, which confirmed that environmental factors and recognition-related motivators were

significant predictors of turnover intention, with environmental factors exerting the stronger negative effect. Organizational commitment, however, was not a significant predictor, suggesting that retention strategies must prioritize improvements in workplace conditions alongside recognition and growth opportunities.

Overall, the study concludes that addressing both hygiene and motivator factors simultaneously is essential to maintain low turnover intention and strengthen organizational commitment among nurse educators. These findings are consistent with Herzberg's assertion that satisfaction and dissatisfaction are driven by distinct sets of factors, and they challenge assumptions that organizational commitment alone can sustain retention. The study contributes to nursing education literature by emphasizing the need for targeted institutional strategies such as structured recognition systems, leadership development, expanded graduate study opportunities, and improved compensation packages to sustain faculty stability and enhance the long-term quality of nursing education in Pampanga and the Philippines.

Recommendations

Given the predominance of early-career and modestly compensated nurse educators in Pampanga's tertiary schools, institutions and policymakers must prioritize targeted strategies that foster professional growth and retention such as: Establish Graduate Scholarship Programs for master's and doctoral studies and review and adjust salary scales to align with workload and qualifications.

In light of the findings that motivational factors significantly influence nurse educators' positive perceptions of their work environment, it is recommended that private institutions in Pampanga prioritize strategies that enhance intrinsic motivation by establishing a structured program that provides nurse educators with opportunities for leadership training, recognition, and academic advancement such as: Leadership Development Workshops, Recognition System and Academic Advancement Support.

To sustain the low turnover intention and reinforce satisfaction and long-term commitment among nurse educators in private institutions, schools must proactively address unmet professional expectations, particularly in recognition of achievements and organize faculty engagement activities such as retreats, collaborative research projects, and committee participation to build belongingness.

To reduce turnover intention and strengthen long-term commitment by addressing both hygiene (fair compensation, supportive leadership, working conditions) and motivator factors (meaningful teaching roles, recognition, career growth), institutions should focus on: Fair Compensation & Benefits (health insurance, wellness packages, conference sponsorships) and meaningful Teaching Engagement.

Create a turnover retention program based on the result of the study.

Recommended Faculty Retention and Development Program for Nurse Educators

Introduction and Background

The sustainability of nursing education in private higher education institutions in Pampanga is challenged by the rising need of nurse educators. Findings from this study revealed that both hygiene factors such as compensation, workload balance, leadership support, and institutional resources and motivator factors such as recognition, career advancement, and opportunities for professional growth—significantly predict faculty retention outcomes. Guided by Herzberg’s Two-Factor Theory, these results underscore the need for a structured retention program that simultaneously addresses the prevention of dissatisfaction and the promotion of satisfaction.

The proposed program, “**MOTIVATE & MAINTAIN: A Dual-Factor Retention Program for Nurse Educators**,” was developed in direct response to these findings. It integrates evidence-based strategies that strengthen organizational commitment, reduce turnover intention, and enhance job satisfaction. By aligning institutional practices with both hygiene and motivator dimensions, the program aims to foster faculty stability, ensure compliance with CHED standards, and sustain the quality of nursing education in Pampanga’s private higher education institutions.

1. Program Title

“MOTIVATE & MAINTAIN: A Dual-Factor Retention Program for Nurse Educators”.

2. Rationale

The retention program is anchored in Herzberg’s Two-Factor Theory, combining motivator factors (recognition, career advancement, research opportunities) with hygiene factors (fair compensation, balanced workload, supportive leadership, adequate resources) to enhance job satisfaction and reduce turnover intention. The program offers a comprehensive, evidence-based framework that strengthens faculty stability and sustains the quality of nursing education in private higher education institutions.

3. Program Objectives

- a. Enhance Job Satisfaction through Motivator Factors: Provide recognition systems, career advancement opportunities, and research incentives to strengthen faculty motivation and commitment.
- b. Reduce Job Dissatisfaction through Hygiene Factors: Ensure fair compensation, balanced workload distribution, supportive leadership practices, and adequate teaching resources to minimize turnover intention.
- c. Strengthen Organizational Commitment and Faculty Stability: Integrate both motivator and hygiene strategies into a unified retention framework that fosters long-term loyalty and sustains the quality of nursing education.

4. Expected Outcomes

- a) **Improved Job Satisfaction.** Faculty satisfaction scores increase by at least 15% within one academic year, reflecting the impact of motivator factors such as recognition and professional growth.
- b) **Reduced Turnover Intention.** Turnover intention rates decrease by 10% within two academic years, supported by hygiene factors like fair compensation, fair workload distribution and supportive leadership.
- c) **Strengthened Organizational Commitment.** Nurse educators demonstrate higher levels of loyalty and engagement, as measured through commitment surveys and retention data.
- d) **Sustainable Faculty Workforce.** Institutions maintain at least 85% faculty retention over the program’s time frame, ensuring stability in nursing education delivery.
- e) **Enhanced Institutional Reputation.** By integrating motivator and hygiene strategies, institutions achieve stronger accreditation outcomes and recognition for faculty support initiatives.

5. Scope and Coverage

This program applies to all full-time and part-time nurse educators in private higher education institution. It involves collaboration among the College of Nursing, Human Resources Department, Academic Affairs, and partner health institutions.

6. Program Components/Strategies

Program Component	Strategies	Expected Outcomes
Workplace Environment (Hygiene Factor)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure competitive compensation and timely salary adjustments (based on Academic qualifications, Performance evaluation and tenure) 2. Provide adequate teaching resources and modern facilities(Procurement of applicable mannequins and models for Nursing Arts Laboratory) 3. Establish clear workload distribution policies(Workload assignment based on qualification, experience and expertise) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Reduced dissatisfaction related to pay, resources, and workload b. Improved perception of fairness and institutional support
Faculty Development (Motivator Factor)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Offer continuous professional development workshops and seminar (Scholarship for advance studies, ensure National and International attendance to work-related seminars, In-service training seminars) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Increased professional growth opportunities b. Higher faculty motivation and

Program Component	Strategies	Expected Outcomes
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Provide research grants, publication incentives, and conference funding (Provisions of financial grants and incentives for faculty researchers) 3. Implement instructional coaching and career development support programs pairing junior and senior faculty 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> c. Strengthened organizational commitment
Leadership Support (Hygiene + Motivator Factor)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote participatory leadership and transparent communication (Team building activities and faculty retreat) 2. Establish faculty recognition programs (e.g., teaching excellence awards, service awards) 3. Provide counseling and wellness initiatives (Annual wellness activities such as rest and recreations, mini sports fest, annual medical check-up) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Enhanced trust between faculty and administrators b. Greater recognition of faculty contributions c. Improved morale and reduced turnover intention
Workload Management (Hygiene Factor)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Implement balanced teaching loads and flexible scheduling 2. Encourage collaborative teaching models 3. Regularly review workload policies to prevent burnout 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Reduced stress and improved work-life balance b. Lower incidence of faculty burnout c. Increased retention rates
Policy Integration & Institutional Alignment (Hygiene + Motivator Factor)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Formalize retention policies aligned with CHED standards 2. Integrate retention strategies into accreditation frameworks - Conduct biannual evaluations of program effectiveness 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Sustainable retention framework embedded in institutional policy b. Compliance with CHED competency-based standards c. Long-term faculty stability and enhanced institutional reputation

7. Program Evaluation Plan

1. Evaluation Objectives

- a. Assess the effectiveness of the retention program in improving job satisfaction and reducing turnover intention among nurse educators.
- b. Determine the impact of motivator and hygiene factor interventions on organizational commitment.
- c. Provide evidence-based recommendations for program refinement and sustainability.

2. Evaluation Methods

- a. Surveys: Administer standardized faculty job satisfaction and organizational commitment surveys every semester.
- b. HR Data Analysis: Track turnover rates, exit interview results, and retention statistics annually.
- c. Focus Group Discussions: Conduct biannual sessions with nurse educators to gather qualitative feedback on program components.
- d. Performance Metrics: Monitor participation in professional development, faculty coaching, and recognition programs.

3. Indicators of Success

- a. Job satisfaction scores increase by at least 15% within one academic year.
- b. Turnover intention decreases by 10% within two academic years.
- c. At least 85% faculty retention rate maintained over the program's time frame.
- d. 100% participation in at least one professional development activity per semester.

4. Timeline

- a. Short-term (Year 1): Baseline survey, initial implementation monitoring, and semester-end evaluation.
- b. Medium-term (Year 2): Comparative analysis of satisfaction and turnover data, mid-program adjustments.
- c. Long-term (Year 3): Comprehensive impact report presented to institutional administrators and CHED.

5. Responsible Units

- a. College of Nursing (program oversight and faculty engagement).
- b. Human Resources Department (data collection and policy integration).
- c. Academic Affairs Office (curriculum alignment and CHED compliance).

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author affirm that this study was conducted in full compliance with ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to participation, and they were assured of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. Anonymity and confidentiality were strictly maintained, with no identifying information disclosed in the reporting of results. Data privacy protocols were followed in accordance

with national and institutional guidelines, and the well-being of respondents was safeguarded throughout the research process. The author declare that no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of this study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all sources were properly acknowledged. The interpretation of findings was conducted without bias, and the results were used purely for academic and research purposes. For full disclosure, the authors acknowledge that artificial intelligence (AI) assistance was utilized in the refinement of writing and formatting, but all substantive content, analysis, and conclusions remain the responsibility of the researcher.

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